

Influence of Social Buffering on the Development of Complex Brain Functions in Homo sapiens: A Theoretical Analysis

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Abstract

This article investigates the influence of social buffering on the development of complex brain functions in Homo sapiens. It is proposed that social buffering may have gradually enhanced the optimization of working memory by reducing stress levels and fostering neurogenesis, thus promoting the development of complex brain functions during the Paleolithic era. Through this study, we explore how these complex interactions may have played a fundamental role in the development of the modern human mind. Finally, this analysis offers new perspectives on the underlying mechanisms in the development of complex brain functions, emphasizing the relevance of social interactions in human evolution.

Keywords: Social Buffering; Complex Brain Functions; Homo sapiens; Evolutionary Psychology; Anthropology; Cognitive Neuroscience

Introduction

This article investigates how social interactions may have shaped cognitive abilities in *Homo sapiens*. From a theoretical perspective, this analysis explores how social buffering may have enhanced the optimization of working memory and, consequently, its likely contribution to the development of complex brain functions. By examining the probable causes that could have driven the optimization of working memory through social buffering, we seek to offer new perspectives on how these influences may have shaped the modern human mind.

Development of Complex Brain Functions in *Homo sapiens*

Complex brain functions (CBF), or cognitive processes, represent the product of emerging bioactivities from the telencephalon through independent cortical circuits (Rakic, 2009; Bunge, 2010; Gazzaniga, 2018). These circuits interact synergistically, promoting interactions between the nervous system, other organism systems, and the environment to ensure integrated functioning that allows for information processing and the generation of predictive models of reality (Bruner, 2023; Hawkins et al., 2019; Nicolelis, 2022). They also encompass a wide range of ontogenetic-phylogenetic factors aimed at generating efferent responses that favor individual genetic expression (Sapolsky, 2017; Dawkins, 1976).

During the 19th and 20th centuries, it was believed that the increase in brain size during the evolution of *Homo sapiens* (HS) was related to the emergence of CBF. However, despite modern HS having the highest encephalization quotient among mammals, this correlation does not imply causality regarding the development of CBF (DeFelipe, 2011; Herculano-Houzel, 2012); apparently, the absolute size of the brain is not the determining factor. Currently, it is suggested that the quantity of neurons, as well as their organization and connectivity, play a crucial role in the modern human mind; these characteristics seem to depend on genetic and environmental factors (DeFelipe, 2022).

Herculano-Houzel (2012, 2016), points out that HS possess approximately 86 billion neurons, which grants them a relevant biological capacity for information processing and exploring various cognitive possibilities. Similarly, she indicates that cooking played a fundamental role in the increase in the number of neurons and the development of CBF, as the manipulation of lithic tools and fire for food pre-processing provided an optimization of caloric intake and energy availability, allowing for the consumption of more food in less time.

On the other hand, Coolidge & Wynn (2005, 2009, 2020), suggest that the development of CBF could be the result of a gradual optimization of Working Memory (WM). WM is a cognitive system composed of multiple components, including the central

executive, the visuospatial sketchpad, the phonological loop, and the episodic buffer (Baddeley & Hitch, 1974), all of which are related to the association cortices of the parietal, temporal, and frontal lobes (Baddeley, 1992, 2000, 2017, 2021; Chai et al., 2018; Bruner, 2023).

These components allow for the simultaneous storage, processing, and modification of information necessary to carry out CBF temporarily and are crucial in everyday tasks such as language, problem-solving, and decision-making (Spencer, 2020; Sánchez-Vincitore et al., 2023).

Within an evolutionary context, WM appears to be the product of anatomic-functional modifications in cerebellar and lateral parietotemporal areas, known for their involvement in WM. These modifications coincide with cognitive and cultural differences that emerged during the Paleolithic, approximately 30,000-100,000 years ago, a period in which a more abstract creation and application of technology is observed according to archaeological records (Coolidge & Wynn, 2005, 2009, 2020; Wynn & Coolidge, 2011; Neubauer et al., 2018; Gunz et al., 2019; Read et al., 2022; Rosales-Reynoso et al., 2018).

Considering all the foregoing, it is likely that the neural modifications and archaeological records reflect gradual cognitive changes in HS, indicating an improvement in WM necessary for symbolic-abstract thinking and the elaboration of complex artifacts.

WM would play a critical role in enabling the handling and integration of information in real-time, which can be reflected in the manipulation of lithic tools and fire for increased caloric intake. Additionally, it enables HS to adapt to changes in the environment and manage multiple elements.

However, despite the likely impact of cooking on the emergence of new neurons and the probable role of WM within this process, the reasons that drove the development of the brain and CBF are still not fully understood (Rosales-Reynoso et al., 2018).

As we explore the various factors that may have contributed to the development of CBF in HS, an aspect emerges that deserves careful analysis: social buffering (SB). This phenomenon is characterized by reducing the adverse effects of stress through social interaction. This notion, though rarely explored in this context, could have played an essential role in the optimization of WM and, consequently, in the development of CBF in HS.

After proposing how the optimization of WM and its probable anatomic-functional modifications in specific encephalic areas coincide with cognitive and culinary changes that may have driven the development of CBF during the Paleolithic, it is essential to analyze how SB could have contributed to this process.

Social Buffering

Based on the probabilistic framework suggesting that anatomo-functional changes in cerebellar and lateral parieto-temporal areas are associated with the optimization of WM, and that this optimization could have been an essential factor driving the development of CBF through cooking, we are confronted with the enigma of understanding the underlying reasons that may have favored the optimization of WM; in this context, we explore SB as a means to elucidate probable causes that allowed WM to be a critical factor in this evolutionary process.

SB is a phenomenon in which social interactions can buffer the adverse effects of stress in various species, including rodents, birds, non-human primates, and humans. This is because the presence of other members of the species suggests the availability of resources to cope with multiple adversities. At the neurobiological level, it has been evidenced that SB can have a favorable impact on neuronal circuits and synapses, promoting adaptations that counteract the adverse effects of stress (Kikusui et al., 2006; Avellaneda & Kamenetzky, 2021; Qi et al., 2021).

Avellaneda & Kamenetzky (2021), indicate that SB could play a crucial role in all stages of human development, as the human brain is one of the most immature at birth. The mother is fundamental in reducing stress during infancy, and individuals of the same age, in later stages of life. Consequently, this could have driven the formation of social structures such as families, herds, and clans, seeking to protect offspring and ensure resources (León & Cárdenas, 2011).

In this sense, the HS brain may have evolved to manage complex social systems (Dunbar & Shultz, 2007; Dunbar, 2009), as it relies on an intricate neuronal network designed to learn, interpret, and respond to the complexities of social interaction (Meyer et al., 2012; Sakyi et al., 2015; Mao et al., 2020; De Felice et al., 2022; Wang & Yuan, 2022; Huang & Lajoie, 2023; Zhang et al., 2023; Oesch, 2024). Consequently, HS may have developed their thinking and shaped their behavior towards social interaction, acquiring knowledge through contact with other members of the same species (Vygotsky, 1978).

Given that the presence of other members suggests the availability of resources to cope with multiple adversities, social interaction can act as a mechanism that could have a favorable impact on HS. This phenomenon has been the subject of numerous investigations that support its effectiveness. Below are some relevant findings:

- *Social Interaction and Stress Modulation*

In the study of mental health, various methodologies have contributed to findings regarding social interaction and stress modulation. Using mixed linear models, scales

measuring anxiety, depression, and stress, as well as electrocardiogram measurements, surveys, and ecological momentary assessment, it has been noted that high-quality and frequent social interactions can exert a protective effect against depressed mood and loneliness (Kuczynski et al., 2021). Furthermore, it has been observed that having better social relationships is associated with reduced depressive symptoms and risk of depression, and higher levels of social support are associated with better mental health outcomes (Sommerlad et al., 2021).

Similarly, it is indicated that exposure to different urban outdoor natural environments and diverse groups of people can increase mental health benefits and promote the recovery of stress-related mental disorders (Song & Lin, 2022). Additionally, it has been highlighted that anxiety levels decrease through social interaction with familiar individuals, regardless of gender, and the interaction with the individual (Gründahl et al., 2023).

On the other hand, social interactions appear to have a modulating effect on stress levels and momentary mood during periods of high stress and loneliness (Forbes et al., 2023). These findings underscore the vital role that social interactions play in reducing stress levels, improving mental health, and enhancing emotional well-being.

- *Social Interaction and Neurogenesis*

Social interaction could also drive neurogenesis in the hippocampus (an area related to memory processes, including WM). Lieberwirth & Wang (2012) and García-Gómez et al. (2022), through a theoretical analysis of the social environment and neurogenesis in the brains of adult mammals and after conducting a systematic review on social behaviors in mice and the possible bidirectional relationship between social behaviors and neurogenesis, indicate that social interactions in HS can modulate neurogenesis in adult HS by facilitating cell proliferation. Additionally, they highlight that social enrichment in mice increases the number of new neurons in the hippocampus compared to isolated mice.

Social Buffering: Potential Role in the Development of Complex Brain Functions

Having laid the conceptual groundwork for SB, it is now pertinent to direct the discussion towards its potential contribution to the development of CBF. In this context, it is essential to emphasize that during the Paleolithic, HS faced adverse conditions for survival, such as food scarcity.

Alt et al. (2022), Ben-Dor & Barkai (2023) and Haushofer & Salicath (2023), indicate that access to food resources during the Paleolithic was scarce, dependent on climatic fluctuations, and could have led to health issues, as well as affecting the ability to cope with

new challenges, pressing HS to adapt to new living conditions and requiring more time to obtain food.

Therefore, we suggest that sustained food scarcity and the psychosocial demand it represented for HS could have triggered a chronic stress response and physiological alterations in the body during the Paleolithic.

Sapolsky (1996, 1999, 2017, 2021), points out that chronic stress leads to prolonged concentration of glucocorticoids, which can have an unfavorable impact on the hippocampus, affecting information retention, recall, inhibiting neurogenesis, causing irreversible neuronal loss, and changes in the amygdala characterized by the generation of intense memories of unfavorable or traumatic events. Additionally, such exposure, along with adverse environmental conditions during the early years of life, can also influence the development of memory and long-term cognitive abilities.

Hjelm et al. (2017), examined this phenomenon in households in Zambia, Africa. After evaluating the impact of unconditional cash transfer programs using a randomized controlled trial method, the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), Household Food Insecurity Access Scale (HFIAS), and ordinary least squares regressions, they indicate that food insecurity is associated with a higher risk of depression and stress due to the lack of adequate food both for the individual and for children who do not receive enough food.

Similarly, Palacios-Barrios & Hanson (2019), indicate that nutritional deficiencies in early childhood have been associated with alterations in brain development and cognitive functioning. This phenomenon can lead to physiological alterations, such as decreased sympathetic reactivity and hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis activity, as well as increased blood pressure.

On the other hand, food scarcity increases ghrelin levels in HS. Ghrelin is a hormone involved in appetite regulation, and high levels of this hormone can trigger anxiety-stress responses (Bremner et al., 2020; Fritz et al., 2020). It has been suggested that ghrelin controls the density of synapses in the hippocampal column, so high levels of ghrelin could be associated with alterations in synaptic plasticity and memory processes (Bouillon-Minois et al., 2021).

Based on this data, we suggest that SB may have countered the adverse effects of chronic stress and gradually generated anatomo-functional changes in cerebellar and lateral parieto-temporal areas, thus optimizing WM functions. This could have facilitated tool manipulation and mastery of fire to improve caloric intake, which in turn could have resulted

in an increase in the number of neurons and the development of CBF, thus supporting the evolutionary process towards adaptation and survival.

The benefit of SB on stress is that it can generate endocrine flexibility by modulating the response of glucocorticoids, with WM being sensitive to the effects of stress-anxiety. Therefore, by modulating stress levels, there is a higher likelihood of improving WM performance (Gilmour & Bard, 2022; Lukasik et al., 2019).

SB could play a crucial role in counteracting the adverse effects of chronic stress, mitigating its impact on mental health and cognitive development. Additionally, it could promote neurogenesis in the hippocampus, which may contribute to cognitive development and optimal brain functioning (Lieberwirth & Wang, 2012; García-Gómez et al., 2022).

High-frequency and high-quality social interaction, as well as mutual support in social groups, can trigger the release of oxytocin, which in turn may have been essential for reducing stress associated with food uncertainty. This hormone, released during SB, has the ability to modulate the effects of stress, protecting neurons and buffering immune-inflammatory responses. In times of food scarcity, this response could have contributed to blocking stress-induced neuronal activity and promoting resilience in HS (Kuczynski et al., 2021; Chun et al., 2022).

Likewise, cooperation in food search and emotional support among familiar individuals may have provided security and a sense of belonging, thereby reducing emotional burden (Sommerlad et al., 2021).

Furthermore, exposure to natural environments and the diversity of individuals may have offered opportunities to obtain food and expand support networks, counteracting stress caused by scarcity (Song & Lin, 2022; Gründahl et al., 2023). In this context, social interactions may have helped regulate stress levels and improve momentary mood, providing well-being and camaraderie in difficult times (Forbes et al., 2023).

This complex interaction could have been fundamental in progressively driving the development of CBF in HS. However, physical activity related to food search could be another possible contributing factor due to the neuroprotective role and the various molecular influences of physical activity on the brain (Raichlen & Polk, 2013; Santiago et al., 2022).

Conclusion

SB may have played a fundamental role in optimizing WM in Paleolithic HS approximately 30,000-100,000 years ago. By regulating stress levels and promoting neurogenesis, SB may have gradually contributed to anatomo-functional changes in cerebellar and lateral parieto-temporal areas, triggering the improvement of WM and abstract

tool manipulation. This progress, in turn, would have driven increased caloric intake through diet and fire control, crucial elements for the subsequent generation of new neurons and the development of CBF. However, it is possible that SB was not the only possible contributing factor.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

ER-A contributed substantially to the conception of the work, interpretation of data, and drafting of the manuscript.

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